

In order to study the nature of the solubilized solutions, surface tension, viscosity, conductivity, zeta potential, of the binary and ternary solutions were measured⁶⁻¹⁰. In case of the binary mixtures,

Fig. 2. Systems (a) Sodium oleate + H₂O, (b) Oleic acid + H₂O, (c) Sodium oleate + H₂O + Oleic acid.

homogeneous curves were obtained while in the ternary solubilized solutions, two peaks were again obtained. The following table gives the concentrations at which the two peaks were formed by studying different properties.

TABLE I.

Properties studies	Concentrations of forming the peaks		References
	First	Second	
Conductivity	$1.338 \times 10^{-6} M$	$3.043 \times 10^{-4} M$	6
Surface tension	6.34	0.95	8
Zeta potential	7.9	1.32	12
Transmission	3.16	3.82	
Viscosity	0.27	2.53	7

It is observed from the table that the two peaks or kinks were not formed at the same concentrations suggesting that during solubilization unstable loose combination of molecules were formed for a very short time making the solution heterogeneous and unstable. Had the solution been homogeneous and stable, kinks or peaks would not have formed¹³.

Acknowledgement

The author is obliged to Prof. A. C. Chatterji, Emeritus Scientist, for suggesting the problem.

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Chlorination of 2-Amino Thiazoles and the Use of Chlorinated Thiazoles as Possible Fungicides

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Manuscript received 9 September 1971, accepted 19 April 1975

IN view of the good response of 2-amino 4-aryl substituted thiazoles and their derivatives as good fungicides¹, it was considered of interest to examine the fungicidal property of a few 2-amino 4-aryl substituted thiazoles and their 5-chloro derivatives, so that a comparison of their fungicidal activity would be possible. The presence of liophilic and polar substituents like aryl and amino groups in the thiazole nucleus, as found here, is expected to augment the fungitoxic property still further². Introduction of halogens³, particularly chlorine, into the thiazole nucleus is expected to increase the fungicidal activity considerably.

2-Amino-4-aryl thiazoles have been synthesized by condensing nine different ketones with thiourea in presence of bromine which is used as the condensing agent⁴. These 2-amino thiazoles were then chlorinated with dry chlorine gas in glacial acetic acid medium, after protecting the amino groups by converting them to their respective hydrochloride salts. In each case a mono chloro derivative resulted.

It has been assumed that the chlorine atom is attached to the thiazole nucleus at C₅-position as the activity of C₅ in the thiazole nucleus is maximum, particularly when there is a substituent at C₂-position⁵. This assumption is further based on the evidences of Garreau⁶ and Ganapathi and Venkataraman⁷ and Mahapatra¹¹. As in this series of thiazoles, the C₄-position is occupied by an aryl group and C₅-position is free; the chlorine atom should enter C₅-position, which generally acts as the *para* carbon atom to the NH₂ group, the orienting group in the molecule. This assumption is further supported by the fact that the chlorinated thiazoles do not undergo coupling with diazotised aniline, which generally takes place at C₅-position, if it is free⁸. The possibility of chlorine atom going to the aromatic part carrying a hydroxy group at C₄-position is also discarded on the ground that the chlorinated compounds do not undergo coupling with diazotised aniline as they should, if chlorine would have entered the phenyl nucleus at C₄-position. This indirectly shows that C₅-position of the thiazole nucleus is not free. This assumption gains further support from the fact that due to the polar effect of the substituents at C₂- and C₄-positions of a heterocyclic compound like thiazole, the newly entering chlorine atom generally attaches to C₅-position⁹.

Experimental

2-Amino-4-phenyl-thiazole: The method used for the preparation of the thiazole was that of Dash and Mahapatra⁴.

NOTES

TABLE 1.—ANALYTICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF 2-AMINO-4-ARYL-5-CHLORO THIAZOLES AND 2-AMINO-4-ARYL THIAZOLES
2-Amino-4-aryl-5-chloro thiazoles

Sl. No.	Nature of the aryl group	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Sulphur		% Halogen		Fungicidal Result— Germination in control slide 95–98%			
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Chlorothiazoles		Simple thiazoles	
								M.E.D. p.p.m.	Dilution for 50% germ. p.p.m.	M.E.D. p.p.m.	Dilution for 50% germ. p.p.m.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	160	68	15.18	15.20	16.52	16.86	20	5	80	20
2.	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	100	62	13.15	13.30	14.55	14.76	20	8	80	22
3.	(p)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	212	65	13.96	14.13	15.56	15.67	20	5	80	20
4.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	181	65	12.82	13.06	28.75	28.98	15	3	70	15
5.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	203	65	10.88	11.05	39.70	39.89	18	4	75	18
6.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	193	70	12.05	12.28	13.52	13.63	20	6	80	20
7.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	190	68	12.11	12.28	13.53	13.63	20	6	80	20
8.	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	127	65	13.33	13.41	14.68	14.88	20	5	80	20
9.	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	125	62	11.78	11.91	13.08	13.22	20	5	80	20

2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-chloro thiazole : The above obtained thiazole (2 g.) was treated with HCl (Conc., 3 ml) and the hydrochloride salt was dissolved in 25 ml of glacial acetic acid, and the mixture was stirred well. Chlorine gas, prepared by the action of Conc. HCl on solid KMnO₄ after successively passing through two towers containing water and Conc. H₂SO₄, was bubbled at a slow and steady rate through this solution taken in another flask until a solid separated. While passing chlorine the flask containing the hydrochloride salt solution of the thiazole was shaken occasionally. The residue was treated with water and was basified with liquor ammonia. The free base liberated was separated by filtration and was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 160°, yield 68%. (Found : S, 15.18; Cl, 16.52; C₉H₇N₂SCl requires S, 15.20; Cl, 16.86%).

Fungicidal test :

The fungicidal assay of the 2-amino thiazoles as well as their 5-chloro derivatives has been done by the method of Montgomery and Moore¹² with slight modification. *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.), the causative organism of rice blast, has been used as the test fungus. The spores were allowed to be kept with fungicides at different dilutions for 24 hr.

The 5-chlorothiazoles are found to be much more active than the non-chlorinated thiazoles. The chloro thiazoles completely inhibit the spore germination at the concentration of 20 p.p.m. and at the concentration of 3 to 5 p.p.m. the spore germination was only 50%. The nonchlorinated thiazoles inhibited the spore germination at a higher concentration of 80 p.p.m. When halogens are present in the aryl nucleus at C₄-position, the fungicidal activity is augmented both in case of 5 chloro and non-chloro

thiazoles. The 5-chloro thiazoles are more active than the corresponding 5-Bromo thiazoles¹¹.

The m.p. yield and analytical data of similarly chlorinated thiazoles are given in Table 1. The results of fungicidal study of all these compounds, both simple and chlorinated thiazoles, (based on dilution necessary for 50% germination and maximum effective dilution) is also given in the same Table.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of Orissa for a research grant and to Dr. S. Y. Padmanavan, Director, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack for allowing the fungicidal test to be done in his laboratory under his direct supervision.

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